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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE PERIODONTAL STATUS OF
PATIENTS RECEIVING ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT**Dr Aqsa Saleem¹, Dr Sidra Nazir², Dr Muhammad Moeed Haider Naqvi³¹ Multan Medical and Dental College² De'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore³ Islam Dental College, Sialkot**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** The purpose of this study was to determine the periodontal condition of patients who sought orthodontic treatment.**Methods:** One hundred patients reported to the orthodontic department were selected between 12 and 25 years of age with complete supplementation of a permanent denture. Significant medical problems, history of antibiotics, orthodontic treatment and smokers were excluded. The community periodontal index was used to assess the periodontal status of these patients. The data of these 100 patients were analyzed using SPSS (version 18.0) on a personal computer.**Conclusion:** The results showed that gingival hemorrhage was the main presentation of patients who came to the orthodontic department for treatment and then mathematics.**Key words:** periodontal condition, patients applying for orthodontic treatment, community periodontal index.**Corresponding author:**Dr. Aqsa Saleem,
Multan Medical and Dental College

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INTRODUCTION:

Orthodontics has become an important part of dental practice. The importance of maintaining oral hygiene should not be overlooked, especially before and during orthodontic treatment¹⁻².

Oral hygiene and periodontal status play a decisive role in planning orthodontic treatment. Periodontal condition of orthodontically treated patients was of interest to orthodontists and periodontists³⁻⁴. The importance of a high level of oral hygiene during orthodontic treatment is to appear before beginning orthodontic treatment. Various studies have been carried out in various parts of the world to assess the oral hygiene status of patients receiving orthodontic devices worldwide⁵⁻⁶. Several studies have been carried out in Pakistan regarding periodontal status of various samples, but not in patients seeking orthodontic treatment⁷.

The purpose of this study was to obtain this data by joining the Society Periodontal Index (CPI) in a sample reporting orthodontic treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

One hundred patients participating in the Department of Dentistry Orthodontics section of Nishter Hospital, Multan for six months duration from February 2019 to July 2019 were randomly selected regardless of gender. Patient ages ranged chronologically from 12 to 25 years. All patients had a complete set of permanent teeth along the first / second molars. Efforts have been made to exclude patients: diabetes, antibiotic therapy over the past two months, abnormal para functional habits, abnormal morphology of hard and soft tissues such as cleft lip and cleft palate, all orthodontic treatment and smoking.

After obtaining informed consent, the authors conducted periodontal examination using the WHO CPI periodontal probe, using the CPI index (Community Periodontal Index), previously known as the CPITN Index (Community Index for the need for periodontal treatment). Each patient's CPI results were recorded and evaluated in accordance with the Appendix.

The mean, standard deviation and range for quantitative variables were calculated using SPSS version 18.0 for Windows. A paired t test was used to determine a significant difference in the periodontal status of 100 patients by sex and oral hygiene method. Twenty patients were randomly selected from a main sample of 100 patients for intra-assay reliability, and CPI results were re-evaluated two weeks after the first study. To gain credibility among the examiners,

patients selected from another colleague from the orthodontic department were asked to assess CPI status. To obtain the credibility of the examiner, the data was analyzed using kappa statistics using SPSS 18.0 software for Windows.

COMMUNITY PERIODONTAL INDEX (CPI)

(Formerly known as Community Periodontal Index of Treatment Needs or CPITN)

Indicators

Three periodontal status indicators are used for assessment:

1. Bleeding gums
2. Periodontal pockets
3. calculus

A specially designed lightweight CPI probe with a 0.5 mm ball tip with black 3.5 mm to 5.5 mm tape and 8.5 and 11.5 mm rings from the end of the ball was used (Figure I).

Sextants

The mouth is divided into sextants defined by tooth numbers: 18-14, 13-23, 24-28, 38-34, 33-43, and 44-48.

S1	S2	S3
18-14	13-23	24-28
48-44	33-43	34-38

S6 S5 S4

Tooth numbering is according to the FDI system. S represents the six sextants and the numbers from 1-6 denotes the number of sextant.

Index teeth

For adults aged 20 years and over, the teeth to be examined are:

17/16 11 26/27
47/46 31 36/37

Two molars on each hind sextant are matched to the record.

Only six teeth for people under 20 years old; 16, 11, 26, 36, 31 and 46. This modification aims to note the deep grooves associated with the series as periodontal pockets. For the same reason, when examining children under 15 years of age, pockets should not be recorded, i.e. only bleeding and calculations should be recorded.

RESULTS:

The average age of 100 patients admitted to the orthodontic clinic was 18.03 ± 3.60 and ranged from

12 to 25 years. For example, the gender distribution was 37% men and 63%

Fig 1. WHO Community Periodontal Index Probe
The percentage of age distribution over the years is clear, indicating that the maximum number of patients, i.e. 15%, is 20 years, 13% and 11%, respectively, 22

and 14 years old. . Regarding oral hygiene, only 5% reported using mouthwash, and the remaining 95% only used toothbrushes and toothpaste. It was found that 58% of patients brushed their teeth twice a day, and the remaining 42% brushed their teeth once or 2-3 days later. Average, minimum and maximum CPI results of six sextants, including cumulative results (Summary of the total CPI score of six sextants) is shown in Table 1. The second sextant (anterior maxillary segment) was found to have a statistically significantly lower mean CPI score than the rest of the five sextants at $p < 0.01$. From Table 2 it was clear that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean CPI results of male and female patients and between six sexes' results and cumulative CPI results ($p > 0.05$). Table 3 shows details of six CPIs in six sextants. The 0 CPI score was 8.16% sex, and score 1 as 62.33% sex.

TABLE 1: CPI SCORE OF 100 PATIENTS

CPI score	Number	Mean CPI Score + SD	Minimum CPI Score	Maximum CPI Score
First sextant	100	1.50 ± 0.81	0	4
Second sextant	100	0.90 ± 0.57	0	3
Third sextant	100	1.41 ± 0.75	0	3
Fourth sextant	100	1.34 ± 0.71	0	3
Fifth sextant	100	1.26 ± 0.79	0	3
Sixth sextant	100	1.39 ± 0.64	0	3
Cumulative CPI score	100	7.80 ± 3.11	2	17

TABLE 2: CPI SCORE OF 100 PATIENTS ACCORDING TO GENDER

CPI score	Number	Mean CPI Score + SD	Minimum CPI Score	Maximum CPI Score	p-value
First sextant					
Female	63	1.49 + 0.80	0	4	NS
Male	37	1.51 ± 0.83	0	4	
Second sextant					
Female	63	0.85 + 0.47	0	2	NS
Male	37	0.97 ± 0.72	0	3	
Third sextant					
Female	63	1.38 + 0.74	0	3	NS
Male	37	1.45 ± 0.76	0	3	
Fourth sextant					
Female	63	1.33 + 0.71	0	3	NS
Male	37	1.35 ± 0.71	0	3	
Fifth sextant					
Female	63	1.33 + 0.78	0	3	NS
Male	37	1.13 ± 0.82	0	3	
Sixth sextant					
Female	63	1.39 + 0.68	0	3	NS
Male	37	1.37 ± 0.59	1	3	
Cumulative CPI score					
Female	63	7.79 + 2.94	3	17	NS
Male	37	7.81 ± 3.41	2	17	

NS stands for "Not Significant" $p > 0.05$

TABLE 3: CPI SCORE OF INDIVIDUAL SEXTANTS OF 100 PATIENTS

CPI score	Sextants						Total sextants	Percent %
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth	Sixth		
0	4	21	4	4	14	2	49	8.16
1	56	69	63	68	54	64	375	62.33
2	28	9	21	18	24	27	129	21.16
3	10	1	12	10	8	7	51	8
4	2	0	0	0	0	0	6	0.33
Total sextants	100	100	100	100	100	100	600	99.98

TABLE 4: MAXIMUM CPI SCORE IN 100 PATIENTS

Maximum CPI	Total patients	Percent %
1	37	37
2	45	45
3	16	16
4	2	2
Total	100	100

Fig 2. Percent distribution of age in 100 patients

CPI score	Number	Mean t SD	Minimum	Maximum	p-value
First sextant					
Toothbrush + toothpaste	95	1.53 ± 0.80	0	4	
Toothbrush + toothpaste + mouthwash	5	0.80 ± 0.44	0	1	p < 0.05
Second sextant					
Toothbrush + toothpaste	95	0.92 ± 0.56	0	3	
Toothbrush + toothpaste + mouthwash	5	0.400 ± 0.54	0	1	p < 0.05
Third sextant					
Toothbrush + toothpaste	95	1.43 ± 0.76	0	3	
Toothbrush + toothpaste + mouthwash	5	1.00 ± 0.00	0	1	NS
Fourth sextant					
Toothbrush + toothpaste	95	1.37 ± 0.70	0	3	
Toothbrush + toothpaste + mouthwash	5	0.60 ± 0.54	0	1	p < 0.05
Fifth sextant					
Toothbrush + toothpaste	95	1.29 ± 0.79	0	3	
Toothbrush + toothpaste + mouthwash	5	0.60 ± 0.54	0	1	p < 0.05
Sixth sextant					
Toothbrush + toothpaste	95	1.41 ± 0.66	0	3	
Toothbrush + toothpaste + mouthwash	5	1.00 ± 0.00	0	1	NS
Cumulative CPI score					
Toothbrush + toothpaste	95	7.97 ± 3.07	0	17	
Toothbrush + toothpaste + mouthwash	5	4.40 ± 1.51	0	6	p < 0.05

NS stands for "Not Significant" p > 0.05

Calculus (CPI index 2) were found in 21.16% of sextants. Shallow pockets, i.e. CPI score 3 (pocket depth 4-5 mm) is 8%, while deep pockets with pocket depth 6 mm or more (CPI score 4) constitute 0.33% of sex. A score of 4 CPI was found in the first sextant of man and woman (Table 2), which makes her 2 sextants with a total of 600 sextants.

Regarding the details of individual sextants; the first, third, fourth and sixth sextant had the highest CPI score of 1, followed by 2, 3 and 0. In the second sex, the CPI score followed 0, 2 and 3. For the fifth result, after gender CPI, the score was 2, 0 and 3. This shows that CPI 1 has the highest prevalence among six sextants. Table 4 clearly shows that 45 patients had CPI 2 as the maximum CPI for any of the six sextants, followed by CPI 1 of 37, score 3 of 16 and score 4 of 2, Table 5 shows the distribution of average CPI scores 100 patients according to the oral hygiene method. Although only 5% used mouthwash, the average CPI scores were significantly lower than the average CPI scores of patients using a toothbrush and toothpaste, with only $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION:

Periodontal condition of patients receiving permanent orthodontic appliances is of interest to both orthodontists and periodontists⁹⁻¹⁰. It is believed that the greater permanent nature of the plaque of orthodontic devices helps plaque formation on the edges of the gums and contributes to gingivitis. The purpose of this study was to determine the periodontal condition of patients reported to an orthodontic clinic for consultation. The trial consisted of 100 patients, regardless of gender, who informed the orthodontic department about seeking treatment. Although periodontal condition in patients using the mouthwash was significantly better ($p < 0.05$) than in patients using only routine rinsing methods (Table 5), the number of these patients was only 5%. Less attention is paid to additional oral hygiene products in our environment. Similarly, only 58% reported brushing teeth twice a day, and 36% reported brushing teeth once a day¹¹⁻¹². The remaining 6% were less interested in regular oral hygiene practices. The second sextant (anterior jaw section) had statistically significantly better periodontal status than posterior oral sections (Table 1). This is in line with the research of Per Gjermo and his partners with 15-year-old Brazilian school children. Gingival bleeding (CPI 1) was found in 374 of 600 sexes (62.33%), making it the most common periodontal disease (Table 3). The second most commonly used application was found in 127 sexes (21.16%)¹³. Healthy sextants and shallow pockets had almost similar frequency (8.16% and 8%, respectively). Only two sextants showed deep bags (CPI score of 4). When it comes to gender details, bleeding gums is the most common finding. The results of this study showed a higher incidence of bleeding gums and tartar compared to the following studies;

Abdul Qadir Khoro, Department of Oral Surgery, Liaquat Medical College Hospital, Hyderabad, Pakistan, 67% of patients had shallow stones or pockets, 22% of our results. Similar results were seen in other studies elsewhere¹⁴. Therefore, compared to most studies, the prevalence of stone and shallow pockets was low in patients reporting to the orthodontic department. It's because; the youngest age of the patients, and the latter was not selected from the

general population for this study¹⁵. Instead, these patients asked for consultation on orthodontic treatment and could be considered as patients motivated to maintain oral hygiene.

CONCLUSIONS:

Patients who went to the orthodontic department for orthodontic treatment most often found bleeding gums in 62% of the sextants, followed by healthy gum, calculus and shallow pockets. Deep pockets were found only in two sextants.

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